

Monitoring of Pesticide Poisoning in Different Occupational Groups by the Estimation of Serum Cholinesterase (PChE), ALT, AST & Bilirubin

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author CMMH involved in designing and planning, investigations and modify the manuscript. Author HMJ performed the data analysis, interpretation and wrote the manuscript. Authors MH and MSR provided assistance in data collections also supervised in data collections. Authors RHC and FN edited and modify the manuscript. Author TBE revised the manuscript and also helped in the grammatical corrections. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: An increasing number of reports suggest that chemical and physical agents in the environment, introduced and spread by human activity may affect human liver. The present study

was conducted to find out pesticide poisoning and its possible effect on liver by assaying PChE, ALT, AST & bilirubin in different occupational groups those are routinely exposed to pesticides.

Materials and Methods: Epidemiological studies focusing on exposure to pesticide and its impact of poisoning in liver. A total of 75 adult males were included in the study. Study subjects/Pesticides sprayer were divided into three groups according to their occupations- working in vector control campaign (Group-A), Farmer (Group-B), Control (Group-C). Members of the first two groups are directly involved in pesticide preparation & spraying. Blood samples were collected from the study subjects by venipuncture and serum was separated and tested for PChE, ALT, AST and bilirubin by spectrophotometer.

Results: In the present study the mean (\pm SD) of serum PChE in the Group-A and Group-B were found 4087.83 ± 1444.23 U/L and 8890.03 ± 2717.75 U/L respectively. In Group-C the mean (\pm SD) of serum PChE was 10357.92 ± 3106.02 U/L. Decrease in PChE activity was observed in the occupationally exposed groups as compared to control group (One-way ANOVA; $p < 0.000$). The mean (\pm SD) of serum ALT in the Group-A, Group-B and Group-C was 21.76 ± 5.59 U/L, 13.88 ± 5.23 U/L, and 16.96 ± 6.25 U/L respectively. The mean (\pm SD) of serum AST in the Group-A and Group-B was 24.96 ± 4.06 U/L and 19.44 ± 4.88 U/L respectively. In Group-C the mean (\pm SD) of serum AST was 22.24 ± 6.11 U/L. Both the liver enzymes ALT and AST show a negative correlation to the PChE. But the ALT level was much higher in sprayer group and shows significant correlation with PChE (Spearman Correlation Coefficient, $r_s = -0.619^{**}$, $p < 0.001$). The mean (\pm SD) serum bilirubin in the Group-A, Group-B and Group-C was 0.888 ± 0.422 U/L, 0.5120 ± 0.303 U/L and 0.644 ± 0.335 U/L respectively. Bilirubin level also shows a significant negative correlation with PChE activity in both Group-A and Group-B, $r_s = -0.560^{**}$, and $r_s = -0.627^{**}$ respectively.

Conclusions: Epidemiological studies suggest awareness of poisoning of pesticide an environmental factor that may affect biological system. Warning labels of pesticides fail to inform users of long-term health dangers. Research into the impact of pesticides on workers' health, diagnostic tests would confirm overexposure to most classes of pesticides, reduced activity of PChE in occupationally exposed people was observed. An elevated level of liver enzymes and bilirubin was found also. Continuous and prolonged exposure to pesticides (organophosphorous) resulted in the decreased PChE activity and increased AST, ALT & bilirubin.

Keywords: Pesticide poisoning; serum cholinesterase (PChE); ALT; AST; bilirubin.

1. INTRODUCTION

The health hazards of pesticides are a major concern internationally especially in developing countries, where pesticides are widely used in agriculture. Most of the pesticides belong to extremely and highly hazardous category as classified by WHO [1]. Each year billions of tons of such toxic chemicals are produced and applied for various purposes- in agriculture, vector control campaign etc. But over 95% of sprayed pesticides reach a destination other than their target species, including non-target species, air, water, bottom sediments, and food. They are considered as one of the common pollutant in the environment [2].

People are commonly exposed to pesticides through eating fresh and processed vegetables, contacting pesticide-contaminated surfaces, breathing air near pesticide applications (both indoors and outdoors), and drinking pesticide-contaminated water. But occupationally exposed people are in serious risk. They come to direct contact with pesticides regularly. Several health

problems were reported in various occupationally exposed groups [3].

Because of long residual effects, agricultural use of organochlorines has been restricted in many countries including Bangladesh. Now organophosphorus insecticides are extensively used for the control of almost all types of insect pests. About 77% of the insecticides in current use in the world are organophosphorus. In Bangladesh a good number of organophosphorus pesticides are available. Malathion, Diazinon (Basudin), Bidrin, Dimecron, Azodrin, Nogos, Nexion etc are best-known organophosphates [4-8].

The usual toxicological effects of the organophosphorus pesticides are due to the inhibition of acetylcholinesterase. Inhibition occurs in synapses and neuromuscular junctions which lead to the accumulation of acetylcholine at synapses, causing overstimulation of both central and peripheral nervous systems [9,10]. This results in respiratory, myocardial and neuromuscular transmission impairment.

All the forms of acetylcholinesterase enzyme in different species such as insects, fish, birds, humans and other mammals can be poisoned by these chemicals. Mineau reported that after exposure to carbamate and organophosphate cholinesterase activity in wild birds decreased [11]. Parson et al. [12] observed similar effect of organophosphate and carbamate on non-target wild animals.

However, there are wide range of disorders have been reported following organophosphorus poisoning and it is becoming apparent that, although inhibition of cholinesterase plays a key role in the toxicology of organophosphates, but only the inhibition of cholinesterase cannot be the reasonable explanation.

As most of the OP pesticides are highly lipid-soluble agents they are well absorbed from the skin, oral mucous membranes, conjunctiva and gastrointestinal and respiratory routes. These are then transported through blood, lymph to the various organs, most abundant in liver, kidney, lungs, bone, followed by muscle and low levels in brain tissue and there interfere with normal functions.

According to WHO, approximately 25 million pesticide poisoning cases occur annually among agricultural workers in developing countries. However, pesticide poisoning due to occupational exposure is poorly documented in developing countries [13]. In Bangladesh lack of awareness in the workers and improper management of the government pesticide poisoning reaches an alarming situation. Day by day the situation is becoming worse. When more than 56 millions of people are involved in agriculture, health issue of the farmers and other occupationally involved people appear as the main matter of concern.

The aim of this study was to assess the pesticide poisoning in different occupational groups who are exposed to pesticide by determining the serum cholinesterase (PChE) activity along with liver functionality by determination of serum ALT, AST & bilirubin level in exposed and control groups.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Subjects

A total of 75 Bangladeshis was included in this study. The test subjects were divided in to three groups:

Occupationally exposed groups		Control group
Sprayers (Working in vector control campaign)	Farmers	
25	25	25

Subjects were collected by arranging a blood collection program organized by the department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology in the Anti-Malarial Unit of Chittagong City Corporation office. The farmers were collected from Hathazari and Shitacundo of Chittagong region. Controls were selected randomly.

2.2 Instrumentation

2.2.1 Questionnaire

A questionnaire was developed to record data recording- age, sex, history of liver diseases, hypertension, drug history, living status, professions, duration of exposure to pesticides, type of pesticide used, experience, and smoking habit. All the questions are written in "BANGLA".

2.2.2 Anthropometric measurement

a. Height (m)

Standing height was measured using appropriate scales (Detect-Medic, Detect scales INC, USA) without shoes. The patient was positioned fully erect, with the head in the Frankfurt plane.

b. Weight (kg)

The balance was placed on a hard flat surface and checked for zero adjustment before measurement. The subjects stood in the centre of the platform wearing light cloths without shoes. Weight was recorded to the nearest 0.5 kg.

c. Calculation of BMI

Body mass indexes (BMI) of the subjects were calculated using standard formula.

$$\text{BMI} = \text{Weight (kg)} / [\text{Height (m)}]^2$$

2.2.3 Collection of blood samples

The entire blood sample was collected in the morning. Venous blood (5-6ml) was taken by venipuncture with the subject sitting comfortably in a chair in a quiet room. After 10-15 minutes blood sample was centrifuged for 10 minutes at

3000 rpm to obtain serum. Serum is preserved at 2-8°C for biochemical analysis.

2.3 Biochemical Methods

Estimation of serum cholinesterase (AChE) by Bio Quality Rapid Tests Kit.

Cholinesterase hydrolyzed butyrylthiocholine to butyrate and thiocholine. Thiocholine reacts with 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) to form nitro-2-mercapto-5-benzoate according to the following reactions:

The rate of nitro-2-mercapto-5-benzoate formation, measured photometrically, is proportional to the enzymatic activity of cholinesterase in the sample.

2.4 Estimation of Serum Transaminases

Transamination is the process in which an amino group is transferred from amino acid to an α -keto acid. The enzymes responsible for transamination are called transaminases. The substrates in the reaction are α -ketoglutaric acid (α -KG) plus L-aspartate for AST, and a KG plus L-alanine for ALT. The products formed by enzyme action are glutamate and oxaloacetate for AST and glutamate and pyruvate for ALT. Addition of 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine results in the formation of hydrazone complex with the ketoacids. A red colour is produced on the addition of sodium hydroxide. The intensity of colour is related to enzymic activity.

2.5 Estimation of Serum Bilirubin

Conjugated (direct) bilirubin in serum is coupled with diazotised sulphanilic acid to form a red coloured compound. Ascorbic acid is used to stop the coupling reaction, and to eliminate interference by haemoglobin. Caffeine benzoate solution is used to split the unconjugated bilirubin protein complex releasing the bilirubin so that it can react with diazotised sulphanilic acid. The tartrate buffer makes the mixture alkaline and converts the red acid bilirubin to a green coloured compound which shows peak absorbance at 607 nm. At this wavelength the absorbance due to haemoglobin or carotene is minimal.

2.6 Statistical Analysis

Data was analyzed by using software of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and MS Excel. The study subjects were split into three groups. The PChE, ALT, AST and bilirubin level among the three groups were compared by one-way ANOVA. Spearman's correlation coefficient test was performed to evaluate the correlation between PChE activity and other three parameters- ALT, AST & bilirubin within group.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the physical characteristics of the test subjects in occupationally exposed groups and control group. All the test subjects were male (100%). The mean ages of occupationally exposed groups were Mean (\pm SD) 34.60 \pm 8.46 U/L in sprayer group (Gr - A) and 35.44 \pm 8.35 U/L in farmer group (Gr - B). The mean age of control group (Gr - C) was 34.80 \pm 8.68. The mean of experience in sprayer group (Gr- A) was 7.92 \pm 2.82 U/L and in farmer group (Gr-B) it was 11.72 \pm 5.54. The total mean \pm SD experience of occupationally exposed groups was 6.54 \pm 6.06. The mean BMI of exposed group were 20.37 \pm 3.20 U/L in sprayer group (Gr - A) and 21.18 \pm 2.189 U/L in farmer group (Gr - B). The mean BMI of control group (Gr - C) was 21.02 \pm 1.94 U/L. The total mean \pm SD BMI was 20.85 \pm 2.50 U/L. Among the test subjects 36% had smoking habit. It was 36% in sprayer group, 44% in farmer group and 28% in control group. In occupationally exposed groups the use of protective equipments during spraying pesticide were negative (100%). 16% sprayers were aware about pesticide poisoning and it was 12% in farmer group and 36% in control group.

Table 2 shows the clinical findings (health problems) in occupationally exposed groups. The result shows that the common pesticides related symptoms were skin irritation, gastrointestinal problem, dizziness, headache, vomiting etc.

3.1 Correlation between Liver Enzymes, Bilirubin and PChE in Different Occupationally Exposed Groups

The correlation between liver enzymes (ALT and AST) and bilirubin with the PChE in different occupationally exposed groups has been analyzed. The r_s and p -value were obtained from Spearman Correlation Coefficient study.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of study subjects

Parameter	All subjects	Occupationally exposed groups		Control group (C)
		Sprayer (A)	Farmer (B)	
Sex (male/female)	75/00	25/00	25/00	25/00
Age	34.94 ± 8.39	34.60 ± 8.46	35.44 ± 8.35	34.80 ± 8.68
Experience	6.54 ± 6.06	7.92 ± 2.82	11.72 ± 5.54	----
BMI	20.85 ± 2.50	20.37 ± 3.20	21.18 ± 2.189	21.02 ± 1.94
Smoking habit	36%	36%	44%	28%
Alcoholism	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Use of protective equipment (Yes/No)	Yes: 0% No: 100%	Yes: 0% No: 100%	Yes: 0% No: 100%	---- ----
Awareness of pesticide poisoning	Yes: 21% No: 79%	Yes: 16% No: 84%	Yes: 12% No: 88%	Yes: 36% No: 64%

Table 2. Clinical findings among the exposed groups

Symptoms (+)	Total	Sprayer	Farmer
1. Skin Irritation	48%	52%	44%
2. Gastrointestinal problem	38%	48%	28%
3. Breathing problem	22%	28%	16%
4. Cough	48%	44%	52%
5. Blurred vision	24%	28%	20%
6. Headache	48%	64%	32%
7. Dizziness/Numbness of muscle	22%	28%	16%
8. Loss of hair	4%	8%	0%
9. Others	18%	20%	16%

Table 3. Biochemical laboratory tests in the worker and control groups

Parameters	Occupationally exposed groups		Control group (C)	p-value
	Sprayer (A)	Farmer (B)		
Serum PChE (U/L) Mean ± SD	4087.83 ± 1444.23	8890.03 ± 2717.75	10357.92 ± 3106.02	0.000
Serum ALT (U/L) Mean ± SD	21.76 ± 5.59	13.88 ± 5.23	16.96 ± 6.25	0.000
Serum AST (U/L) Mean ± SD	24.96 ± 4.06	19.44 ± 4.88	22.24 ± 6.11	0.001
Serum Bilirubin (mg/dl) Mean ± SD	0.8880 ± 0.422	0.512 ± 0.303	0.644 ± 0.335	0.002

3.2 Correlation between Serum ALT and PChE Activity in Occupationally Exposed Groups

Fig. 1(a) shows the relationship between serum ALT and PChE activity in sprayer group. A significant increase in ALT was observed with the decrease in PChE activity. There was a significant negative correlation ($r_s = -0.619$, and $p < 0.001$). A similar negative relationship was observed between PChE activity and serum ALT ($r_s = -0.136$) in farmer group Fig. 1(b). Some how it was insignificant ($p < 0.509$).

3.3 Correlation between Serum AST and PChE Activity in Occupationally Exposed Groups

Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b) shows the relationship between serum AST and PChE activity in sprayer group (Gr - A) and farmer group (Gr - B). A similar negative but insignificant relationship was observed between PChE activity and serum AST ($r_s = -0.306$, $p < 0.136$; & $r_s = -0.143$ $p < 0.495$).

3.4 Correlation between Serum Bilirubin and PChE Activity in Occupationally Exposed Groups

Fig. 3(a) shows the relationship between serum bilirubin and PChE activity in sprayer group. An

increase in serum bilirubin level was observed with the decrease in PChE activity in both exposed groups. Moreover, the negative correlation ($r_s = -0.560$ & $p < 0.004$ in sprayer group; $r_s = -0.627$, and $p < 0.001$ in farmer group) were highly significant.

Fig. 1(a). Correlation between serum ALT and PChE activity in sprayer group (A)
 [** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)]

Fig. 1(b). Correlation between serum ALT and PChE activity in farmer group (B)
 [** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)]

Fig. 2(a). Correlation between serum AST and PChE activity in sprayer group (A)
 [** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)]

Fig. 2(b). Correlation between serum AST and PChE activity in farmer group (B)
 [** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)]

4. DISCUSSION

In this study Group-A and Group-B occupationally exposed to- malathion malamar (malathion), Basudin (diazinon), delthoate 40EC

(dimethoate), solar 55EC (chloropyrifos + cypermethrin). Farmers use various pesticides but organophosphorous are predominant. Group-A was commonly exposed to malathion used as larvaecide.

Fig. 3(a). Correlation between serum bilirubin and PChE activity in sprayer group
[** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)]

Fig. 3(b). Correlation between serum bilirubin and PChE activity in farmer group
[** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)]

Cholinesterase activity was reported to be decreased in heart attack, liver dysfunction, cancer metastasis, muscular tremors, and neurological disorders. Although its activity is used to monitor the liver dysfunction and neurotoxicity in humans exposed to several toxic chemicals or insecticides. Humans have three

types of cholinesterase e.g., Red blood cell (RBC) cholinesterase, called "true cholinesterase"; Plasma cholinesterase, called "pseudocholinesterase;" (PChE) and Brain cholinesterase. Red blood cell cholinesterase is the same enzyme that is found in the nervous system, while the plasma cholinesterase (PChE)

also known as butyryl cholinesterase is made in the liver. Pseudo cholinesterase (PChE) has a broader range of esterase activity that can hydrolyze butyryl choline, acetylcholine and other aliphatic esters.

Gard and Hooper reported that organophosphors and carbamates exert their effects by binding to and inhibiting the acetylcholinesterase enzyme at nerve synapses [14]. Decrease PChE activities in organophosphorous exposure were also reported previously in rats, when rats were given subcutaneous injections of parathion in different ages [15,16]. Our results were consistent with the previous studies. In the sprayer group the PChE decreased greatly.

Blood cholinesterase measurement, which is the standard method of monitoring, gave no indication of these exposures to organophosphorous compounds in farmer group. There are a number of possible reasons for this lack of sensitivity. First place, spontaneous fluctuations in enzyme activity occur in normal individuals, and in any group of normal subjects there is a wide range of values. Secondly, organophosphorous levels in blood are likely to be highest shortly after exposure, and to decline quickly as dilution occurs in the body fluids. It is unlikely; therefore, that a spot-check of blood cholinesterase activity would reveal any depression unless the sample had been taken shortly after exposure [17,18]. Thirdly, in Bangladesh most of the farmers are poor and they have to cultivate very small amount of land. So they were exposed to pesticides for short period of time. Fourthly, some farmer often used diluted pesticide rather appropriate dose.

All these factors were considered during study design. In our study all the test subjects were male (100%). Females are excluded from the study as PChE activity is greatly changed during pregnancy. The mean (\pm SD) age of the test subjects was 34.94 ± 8.39 and the age of test subject was within the limit (20-50years). All the test subjects are perfectly age matched. The mean age of control group (34.80 ± 8.68) did not vary with the two occupationally exposed groups (34.60 ± 8.46 and 35.44 ± 8.35). The mean BMI of the three groups were within normal range: 20.37 ± 3.20 , 21.18 ± 2.189 , 21.02 ± 1.94 . There was no chance of interference from the malnutrition with the PChE activity.

Laboratory methods for cholinesterase testing differ greatly, and results obtained by one method cannot be easily compared with results obtained by another. Sometimes there is also considerable variation in test results between laboratories using the same testing method. Thus all the samples were tested in the same laboratory, using a consistent testing method [17].

In the absence of additional exposure, blood cholinesterase enzymes will regenerate in about 120 days from very low to normal values in the case of organophosphate poisoning, and more rapidly for carbamate insecticides [19,20]. Cholinesterase testing must be done immediately following exposure to be of much value. The test is ineffective for the carbamate fungicides.

The two transaminases of diagnostic importance are serum glutamic oxaloacetate transaminase (SGOT) or aspartate amino transferase (AST), and serum glutamic pyruvate transaminase (SGPT) or alanine amino transferase (ALT). While AST is found in every tissue of the body, including red blood cells, and is particularly high in the cardiac muscle, ALT is present in moderately high concentration in liver and low in cardiac, skeletal muscle and other tissues. Both AST and ALT measurements are useful in the diagnosis and monitoring of patients with hepatocellular disease. Any abnormality in the liver leads to the elevated activity of the both enzyme in serum.

On the other hand, bilirubin is formed from the haem fragment of hemoglobin released by aged or damaged red blood cells. Liver, spleen and bone marrow are the sites of bilirubin production. Bilirubin formed in spleen and bone marrow is transported to the liver. In the liver it is converted into bilirubin conjugates bilirubin mono and diglucuronides. Any liver disease affects the above systems, and hence bilirubin accumulates in serum leading to jaundice [21-23].

Elevated level of ALT, AST and bilirubin was observed in sprayer group (A). Statistical analysis showed a significant correlation between ALT and PChE. The result was consistent with animal studies. The effect of sub-lethal doses of Malathion and Methyl-parathion was studied on the rat liver enzymes. Intravenous administration of both insecticides at weekly interval for four weeks resulted in

increase in heart and spleen weight. Short term (24 hr.) and long term (4 weeks) treatment with insecticides resulted in increased specific activities of liver enzymes, Acid phosphatase, Alkaline phosphatase, Glutamate dehydrogenase, Glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase and Glutamate pyruvate transaminase [24,25]. An experiment showed that chlorfenvinphos led to an increase of acid hydrolases and glutamic-oxaloacetic and glutamicpyruvic transaminases activity in the serum. The degree of increase in the serum activity of cellular enzymes depended on the magnitude and severity of cell damage [26,27]. The mechanism of this damage is not fully understood. The farmers showed normal level of ALT & AST and slight increase in bilirubin level.

Hair loss was observed in group A & B. Pesticides are rapidly taken up by anagen follicles. The result is disturbances in keratinization: many hairs break within the follicles, while other follicles enter catagen prematurely. Loss of hair is the most consistent symptom [28].

Cough and breathing problem were among the effects on other systems reported in this study. Hayes speculated that about 25% of inhaled pesticide would be re-exhaled, about 50% would be deposited in the upper respiratory passages and subsequently swallowed, and about 25% would be deposited in the lower respiratory passages. This represents a significant occupational hazard [29]. Due to the prevalence of Hep-B all the test subjects were initially screened for hepatitis B to avoid interference with the liver function test. During the selection for control group individuals confirmed that they do not exposed to pesticides for at least 30-45 days [30].

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present study a clear reduced activity of PChE in occupationally exposed people was observed. Also an elevated level of liver enzymes and bilirubin was found. This finding indicates that the continuous and prolonged exposure to pesticides (organophosphorus) resulted in the decreased PChE activity and increased AST, ALT & bilirubin. It is necessary to conduct longitudinal studies with exposure assessment of pesticide poisoning that should focus more on the explanation of the biological mechanisms. This epidemiological

study suggests to aware of environmental poisoning factor pesticide which may affect biological system and both in case of well proven and disputable hazards it is necessary to reduce the exposure of end user (including future ones) to pesticides. The studies conducted in the general population are very rare, mainly because of the difficulties in collecting the samples. This has caused also that some works are small pilot studies.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

It is not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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